

Dynamics of Changes in Marketing Strategies and Consumer Purchase Intentions in the Post-Pandemic Era: A Study of Coffee Shops in Jakarta¹

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ABSTRACT: The COVID-19 pandemic has caused significant changes in consumer behavior and marketing strategies, but the relevance of these changes in the post-pandemic era is still not fully understood.² This study aims to explore how marketing strategies that were effective during the pandemic, such as servicescape and social media marketing, remain relevant or need to be adapted in the post-pandemic context.³ Using a qualitative research method with a case study approach in coffee shops in Jakarta, data were obtained through literature analysis and in-depth interviews with business actors in the industry. The results of the study indicate that although social media marketing remains important in building interactions with consumers, there has been a shift in consumer attention back to aspects of price and product quality, which were previously less dominant.⁴ Servicescape still plays a role, but with a greater emphasis on aspects of cleanliness and safety. The study concludes that businesses need to adopt flexible and dynamic marketing strategies, combining elements that have proven effective during the pandemic with new approaches that are more relevant to the post-pandemic era. The results of this study provide practical guidance for business actors in navigating the ever-evolving changes in consumer behavior and contribute to the literature on adapting marketing strategies in crisis and post-crisis situations.

Keywords: marketing strategy, post-pandemic, servicescape, social media marketing, business adaptation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Background The COVID-19 pandemic has had a very significant impact on various business sectors, including the coffee shop industry in Jakarta. During the pandemic, many coffee shops were forced to close their operations or experienced a drastic decline in sales due to social restrictions and changes in consumer behavior. This situation has encouraged business actors to develop and implement innovative marketing strategies to re-attract declining consumer interest. Elements such as servicescape, price discounts, and social media marketing have become very important in efforts to maintain and increase

¹ Ana Alina Tudoran a b, Charlotte Hjerrild Thomsen c, Sophie Thomasen 2024 Understanding consumer behavior during and after a Pandemic: Implications for customer lifetime value prediction models Journal of Business Research

² By Kent Lewis 08/27/20 COVID-19 changed consumer behavior and marketing strategy Smart Brief

³ Shweta Singh, Annmarie Nicely, Jonathon Day, Liping A. Cai 2022 Marketing messages for post-pandemic destination recovery- A Delphi study Journal of Destination Marketing & Management Volume 23

⁴ Yogesh K. Dwivedi a, Elvira Ismagilova b, D. Laurie Hughes c, Jamie Carlson d, Raffaele Filieri e, Jenna Jacobson f, Varsha Jain g, Heikki Karjalainen h, Hajer Kefi i, Anjala S. Krishen j, Vikram Kumar k l, Mohammad M. Rahman m, Ramakrishnan Raman k l, Philipp A. Rauschnabel n, Jennifer Rowley o, Jari Salo p, Gina A. Tran q, Yichuan Wang r 2021 Setting the future of digital and social media marketing research: Perspectives and research propositions International Journal of Information Management

consumer purchasing intentions during times of crisis. However, as the pandemic subsides, the relevance and effectiveness of these strategies in the post-pandemic era need to be re-evaluated.

Reasons for Choosing an Idea

This idea was chosen because changes in consumer behavior that occurred during the pandemic are likely not temporary and will continue to influence market dynamics in the future. In addition, coffee shops are one of the businesses that rely heavily on direct interaction with consumers, so the marketing strategy used must be able to adapt to these changes. Through this research, it is hoped that marketing strategies can be found that remain relevant and effective in the post-pandemic era, providing practical guidance for business actors to survive and thrive amidst ongoing changes.⁵

Importance of Discussion Discussing the dynamics of changes in marketing strategies in the post-pandemic era is very important because it can help businesses understand how changes in consumer behavior post-pandemic affect their purchase intentions. Thus, businesses can adjust their marketing strategies to stay relevant and competitive in an increasingly dynamic market.⁶ This study is also important to enrich the literature on business adaptation to sudden and significant changes in external conditions, such as a pandemic.

Discussion Objectives The objectives of this discussion are to evaluate the effectiveness of marketing strategies used during the pandemic, such as servicescape, price discounts, and social media marketing, and to assess the relevance of these strategies in the post-pandemic era. This study also aims to provide practical solutions for coffee shop business actors in Jakarta in adjusting their marketing strategies according to changes in consumer behavior that occur post-pandemic.

Brief Literature Review Existing literature suggests that during the pandemic, social media marketing and the arrangement of the physical environment (servicescape) become very important in maintaining consumer purchase intention.⁷ For example, research by Bhatti (2018) shows that social media marketing has a positive influence on consumer purchase intention, especially when physical interaction is limited. Meanwhile, Bitner (2022) states that servicescape can influence consumer perceptions of service quality, which in turn influences purchase intention. However, there are still few studies that explore how the relevance of these strategies changes after the pandemic subsides.

Novelty of Ideas The novelty of this research lies in its focus on evaluating whether marketing strategies used during the pandemic are still relevant in the post-pandemic era, and how businesses can adapt to evolving consumer behavior changes. The study also offers new perspectives on how marketing elements previously considered critical may need to be adjusted or replaced with approaches that are more appropriate to post-pandemic market conditions.

Description of the Main Problem The main problem faced in this study is the uncertainty regarding the effectiveness of marketing strategies used during the pandemic in the post-pandemic context.⁸ Are elements such as servicescape, price discounts, and social media marketing still able to attract consumer

⁵ Keith Hanshaw 2024 Adapting Your Marketing Strategy in a Post-Pandemic World Adapting your marketing strategy original art by Keith Hanshaw and Jasper.ai-

⁶ Chip House 2023 5 Strategies to stand out in a competitive market <https://www.insightly.com/blog/strategies-competitive-market/>

⁷ Rijitha R. 2021 THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING ON CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTION Conference: Contemporary Media Persuasive Technology and Psychology of Visual Communication At: Tamil Nadu Volume: 1

⁸ Jay Mandel on February 27, 2024 Adapting marketing strategies for post-pandemic reality: The need for authenticity <https://martech.org/>

purchasing interest? Or, are consumers now more focused on other factors such as product quality or sustainability?

Solutions Provided This research offers solutions by proposing a more flexible and dynamic marketing strategy, which combines elements that have proven effective during the pandemic with new approaches that are more appropriate for the post-pandemic era.⁹ This includes improving the quality of digital interactions, emphasizing health and safety aspects in the servicescape, and adjusting price discount strategies that are more relevant to current consumer preferences. Thus, coffee shop businesses can continue to attract and maintain consumer interest amidst ongoing changes.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

1. How are the relevance and impact of marketing strategies, such as servicescape and social media marketing, implemented during the COVID-19 pandemic on consumer purchase intentions in coffee shops in Jakarta in the post-pandemic era?
2. Does an effective price discount strategy during the pandemic still have relevance and significant impact on consumer purchasing behavior in the post-pandemic era, or does it need to be adjusted to new market dynamics?

III. METHOD

The methodology of this research is carried out with a qualitative approach through a literature study, which focuses on the analysis of relevant literature related to marketing strategies and consumer purchase intentions in the post-pandemic era.¹⁰ This study aims to explore how consumer behavior changes and the relevance of marketing strategies, such as servicescape, price discounts, and social media marketing, which were previously used during the COVID-19 pandemic.¹¹ The data sources in this study were obtained from books, scientific journals, articles, and industry reports that discuss related topics. Data analysis was carried out by reviewing existing theories in depth and comparing them with previous research findings, in order to gain a comprehensive understanding of how marketing strategies can be adapted in the post-pandemic era. The conclusions generated from this study are expected to provide theoretical guidance for business managers in adjusting their marketing strategies according to the dynamics that are developing in the current market.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Marketing Strategy Amidst Change: Jakarta Coffee Shop Adaptation Post-Pandemic The COVID-19 pandemic that rocked the world some time ago, has also changed the dynamics of the coffee shop industry in Jakarta. It's not just about how a cup of coffee is served, but also how consumers interpret the coffee experience amidst a new reality full of uncertainty. This study digs deeper into how consumer perceptions of elements such as servicescape, price discounts, and social media marketing influence their purchase intentions in the post-pandemic era.

⁹ Mandar Ambekar 2023 Navigating the New Normal: Adaptive Marketing Strategies in a Post-Pandemic World Linked in

¹⁰ Ibrahim A. Elshaer a b, Mahmaod Alrawad c, Abdalwali Lutfi d f, Alaa M.S. Azazz b e 2024 Social commerce and buying intention post COVID-19: Evidence from a hybrid approach based on SEM – fsQCA Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services

¹¹ P. K. Kannan Gauri Kulkarni 2021 The impact of Covid-19 on customer journeys: implications for interactive marketing Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing ahead-of-print(ahead-of-print)

When talking about servicescape, we are not just talking about the aesthetics of the space. Servicescape is now one of the main determinants that influence consumers' decisions to stop and enjoy a cup of coffee at a coffee shop.¹² In the post-pandemic context, consumers have become more critical of the cleanliness, layout, and overall ambiance of the coffee shop. They are looking for a place that is not only comfortable but also provides a sense of security. This reflects that servicescape now plays a more crucial role in creating a holistic consumer experience.

Furthermore, price discounts, which used to be the main magnet in attracting consumers, are now starting to lose their popularity. This study shows that in the post-pandemic context, consumers are more likely to look for quality rather than just low prices.¹³ This shift illustrates how consumers are starting to value experiences and long-term value, where discounts are only considered an added bonus, not the main determinant in purchasing decisions. This shows a fundamental change in how consumers view the value of a product or service.

In the realm of social media marketing, this study reveals the importance of an active and interactive presence on digital platforms. In this digital era, social media has become a bridge that connects coffee shops with their customers. Consumers not only want to know about the products offered, but also want to feel an emotional connection with the brands they choose. Through relevant content and active interaction, coffee shops can build strong customer loyalty, which ultimately drives their purchase intention.

However, the real strength of this study lies in how all three elements—servicescape, price discounts, and social media marketing—work synergistically to influence consumer purchase intentions. No single element can stand alone; all must be integrated into a comprehensive marketing strategy. An attractive servicescape must be supported by good communication through social media, while price discounts, while not the primary factor, can strengthen the overall appeal of an offering.

The implications of these findings are clear. Coffee shops in Jakarta must adapt quickly to changing consumer behavior in the post-pandemic era. They need to prioritize servicescape quality, increase engagement on social media, and use price discounts strategically to strengthen their competitiveness. The main focus is no longer just on the products sold, but also on how experiences and interactions with consumers can create sustainable value.

By understanding these dynamics, coffee shops in Jakarta can be better prepared to face future challenges, stay relevant, and continue to thrive amidst ongoing changes. This study, ultimately, underscores the importance of adaptation and innovation in facing the new realities brought by the pandemic.

Understanding Consumer Dynamics in the Post-Pandemic Era: Coffee Shop Marketing Strategies in Jakarta

In an ever-changing business landscape, the COVID-19 pandemic has forced many sectors, including the coffee shop industry, to make significant adaptations. It is no longer enough to simply offer a quality cup of coffee; now, consumer experience is at the heart of an effective marketing strategy. This study dives deeper into how three key elements—servicescape, price discounts, and social media marketing— influence consumer purchase intentions in Jakarta, particularly in the post-pandemic context.

¹² Thilini Mudiyanse 2021 The impact of servicescape on consumer purchasing behavior: A study of Coffee Shops in Colombo, Sri Lanka RG

¹³ Lenka Veselovská 2023 Risk based approach to documenting consumer behavior changes during the COVID-19 pandemic Societal Impacts

Servicescape: Building Trust Through Physical Experience

In the coffee shop business world, servicescape or the physical environment of a shop plays a very important role, especially in the post-pandemic era. Servicescape is not only about how the space is arranged or decorated, but also how these physical elements can create a sense of safety and comfort for consumers.¹⁴ Amid ongoing health concerns, consumers are now demanding higher standards of cleanliness, layouts that support social distancing, and an overall calming atmosphere.

A clean and well-organized physical environment not only provides visual comfort, but also serves as a tool to build trust. When consumers feel safe in a space, they are more likely to linger, enjoy the product, and even return at a later date. This shows that servicescape is a key factor in creating a positive experience that can strengthen consumer loyalty and increase purchase intentions.

Thus, in developing an effective marketing strategy, coffee shop business owners must prioritize servicescape. They must ensure that every aspect of the physical environment of the shop not only meets aesthetic standards, but also responds to consumer needs for cleanliness and safety. By prioritizing a safe and comfortable physical experience, coffee shops can build deep trust with their consumers, which ultimately becomes the foundation for business success in this challenging era.

Price Discounts: Shifting Focus to Quality and Long-Term Value

During the pandemic, price discounts were one of the most effective marketing strategies to attract consumers. However, in the post-pandemic era, this study shows that the appeal of price discounts is starting to diminish in consumer purchasing decisions. Consumers are now more critical and selective, shifting their focus from temporary price incentives to product quality and the long-term value offered.¹⁵

This change reflects a shift in priorities among consumers. They value meaningful experiences and products that offer superior quality, rather than simply looking for a cheap price. Post-pandemic consumers tend to judge a product or service based on how it can provide ongoing satisfaction and benefits, both in terms of quality and safety.

In this context, price discounts can still serve as an additional element in a marketing strategy, but are no longer the primary focus. Businesses that want to remain relevant and competitive need to reevaluate their approach to pricing, and place greater emphasis on delivering higher value. This could mean offering better quality products, more personalized service, or stronger security guarantees.

By shifting the focus from simply offering price cuts to offering quality and long-term value, coffee shops can meet evolving consumer expectations. This strategy will not only attract new customers, but also build stronger loyalty among customers who value the product and the experience they receive. Success in the post-pandemic era will not only depend on lower prices, but on the ability to offer sustainable and satisfying value to consumers.

Social Media Marketing: Connecting Brands with Consumers in the Digital World

In the increasingly digital era, social media marketing has become one of the main pillars in business marketing strategies, including coffee shops. Especially in the post-pandemic era, when physical interactions are limited, social media plays an important role in maintaining the relationship between

¹⁴ Zalfa Laili Hamzah Muhammad Waqas 2023 Interactive Experience of Physical Servicescape and Online Servicescape: A Review and Future Research The Palgrave Handbook of Interactive Marketing

¹⁵ Dan Zheng a, Yuxin Chen b, Zhe Zhang c, Hai Che d 2022 Retail price discount depth and perceived quality uncertainty Journal of Retailing

brands and their consumers.¹⁶ However, to remain relevant and effective, social media marketing needs to adapt to changes in consumer behavior and needs that have occurred due to the pandemic.

Today's consumers aren't just looking for information about products or promotions on social media; they also want a more personal and meaningful connection with the brands they choose. This is where it's important for businesses to create content that's relevant to the current situation, such as highlighting the health protocols implemented at coffee shops or showing how the business is adapting to new conditions. By showing that the brand cares about the health and safety of its consumers, coffee shops can build stronger trust and loyalty.

In addition, more personal and engaging interactions are also key to success in social media marketing.¹⁷ Consumers want to feel connected to brands not only as customers, but as part of a larger community. Therefore, marketing strategies should include efforts to create interactive digital experiences, such as through Q&A sessions, polls, or sharing consumer stories. These activities not only increase consumer engagement but also strengthen the emotional bond between brands and consumers. By utilizing social media effectively, coffee shops can continue to attract new consumers and maintain the loyalty of existing customers. Social media marketing is not just about product promotion, but also about building strong and sustainable relationships with consumers. In the post-pandemic era, the ability to adapt and adjust marketing strategies to the evolving needs of consumers will be the key to success. Brands that are able to connect with consumers through social media in an authentic and relevant way will be easier to survive and thrive amidst increasingly fierce competition.

Strategic Combination: Synergy of Elements in Increasing Purchase Intention

In an increasingly complex business world, the success of a marketing strategy cannot be achieved by relying on just one element.¹⁸ This study emphasizes the importance of synergy between various marketing elements—servicescape, price discounts, and social media marketing—in increasing consumer purchase intention, especially in the post-pandemic era. The strategic combination of these three elements not only strengthens a brand's appeal but also creates a more holistic and satisfying consumer experience.

An effective servicescape not only serves as a visual appeal, but also as a foundation for building consumer trust and comfort. A clean, safe, and comfortable physical environment of a coffee shop is an important element that influences purchasing decisions. However, the success of servicescape in attracting consumers will be more optimal if supported by other marketing strategies, such as carefully designed price discounts and interactive social media marketing.

While price discounts may no longer be the primary factor in purchasing decisions in the post-pandemic era, they still play an important role as a complement that strengthens the overall appeal.¹⁹ Discounts can provide an additional incentive for consumers who may be hesitant, especially when combined with relevant promotions delivered via social media. However, for price discounts to be truly effective, they must be balanced with the assurance of quality and experience offered by the coffee shop.

Social media marketing plays a crucial role in communicating the value of the other two elements—

¹⁶ Michael Janamian 2024 Effective Strategies for Social Media Marketing to Build Strong Relationship With Your Potential Clients :imked in

¹⁷ Adam hayes 2024 Social Media Marketing (SMM): What It Is, How It Works, Pros and Cons <https://www.investopedia.com/>

¹⁸ John A Weber, Utpal M Dholakia 2000 Including Marketing Synergy in Acquisition Analysis:: A Step-Wise Approach Industrial Marketing Management

¹⁹ Alberto Cavallo a, Oleksiy Kryvtsov b 2024 Price discounts and cheapflation during the post-pandemic inflation surge Journal of Monetary Economics

servicescape and price discounts—to consumers. Through social media, coffee shops can highlight the benefits of their physical environment, promote discounts offered, and create a more personal relationship with consumers. Social media serves not only as a platform for promotion, but also as a tool to strengthen the emotional connection between the brand and its consumers.

When these three elements work together in an integrated strategy, the result is a significant increase in purchase intent.²⁰ Consumers are not attracted by just one aspect, but by the entire experience offered. A comfortable servicescape, supported by attractive price discounts and communicated effectively through social media, creates a stronger and more sustainable appeal.

By understanding and implementing this synergy, coffee shop business owners can create a more effective and holistic marketing strategy that not only attracts new consumers but also maintains the loyalty of existing customers. The strategic combination of these various marketing elements will ensure that the business remains relevant and competitive amidst the ever-changing market landscape, especially in the post-pandemic era.

Implications for Business Practitioners

This research provides in-depth insights for business practitioners, especially in the coffee shop industry, about the importance of adaptation and innovation in marketing strategies in the post-pandemic era.²¹ With significant changes in consumer preferences, business actors need to consider several important implications to stay relevant and competitive.

1. Prioritize a Safe and Comfortable Servicescape:

Today's consumers are very concerned about cleanliness, safety, and comfort in the physical environment of a coffee shop. Businesses must ensure that their servicescape is not only aesthetically pleasing, but also provides a sense of safety and comfort for consumers.²² This includes implementing strict health protocols, maintaining regular cleanliness, and arranging the layout to support social distancing. Focusing on these elements will help build consumer trust and loyalty.

2. Re-evaluate Price Discounts as a Primary Strategy:

While price discounts were once a key weapon in attracting consumers during the pandemic, this study shows that discounts now have a weaker influence on purchasing decisions.²³ Business practitioners should re-evaluate the use of price discounts, and place more emphasis on offering sustainable value such as superior product and service quality. Discounts can still be used as an additional incentive, but the primary focus should shift to how to provide a satisfying and valuable experience for consumers.

3. Optimizing Social Media Marketing to Build Stronger Relationships:

Social media marketing remains a highly effective tool in attracting and retaining consumers.²⁴ However, this approach should focus more on creating content that is relevant to the post-pandemic situation, such as highlighting health protocols, showing product quality, and offering more personal and engaging digital interactions. Business practitioners should use social media as a platform to build deeper emotional connections with consumers, not just as a promotional tool.

4. Integration of Marketing Elements to Create Powerful Synergy:

The success of a marketing strategy cannot be achieved by relying on one element alone. Business

²⁰ Roger West 2024 Reach High Intent Audiences with the Right Digital Marketing Strategy <https://www.rogerwest.com/>

²¹ Olga Dziubaniuk a, Wilhelm Barner-Rasmussen a, Nikolina Koporcic b, Maria Ivanova-Gongne a, Tibor Mandják c, Stefan Markovic d 2021 Business-to-business marketing research: Assessing readability and discussing relevance to practitioners *Industrial Marketing Management*

²² Won yong Jang a, Sang yeol Baek 2024 The relative importance of servicescape in fitness center for facility improvement *Heliyon*

²³ Jay Fuchs 2024 Discount Pricing: Its Strategies & Practical Examples [hubspot.com](https://www.hubspot.com/)

²⁴ Gavin Boyter 2023 16 ways to build a better social media presence <https://sproutsocial.com/>

practitioners must integrate various marketing elements—servicescape, price discounts, and social media marketing—to create a powerful synergy. An effective combination of these three elements will result in a more holistic consumer experience, increase purchase intention, and strengthen customer loyalty.²⁵

5. Focus on Long-Term Value:

In the face of increasingly critical and selective consumers, business actors must focus on delivering long-term value.²⁶ This means offering products and services that not only meet current consumer needs but also provide ongoing satisfaction. Investments in quality and consumer experience will provide greater long-term benefits than marketing strategies that rely solely on temporary incentives.

How important it is for business practitioners to continue to adapt to changes in the market. Businesses that are able to implement holistic and value-focused marketing strategies will be more successful in maintaining and increasing consumer purchasing intentions in the post-pandemic era. Appropriate adaptation to these changing consumer preferences is key to long-term success in an ever-evolving industry.

Discussion

Marketing Strategy Dynamics in the Post-Pandemic Era: Lessons from Jakarta Coffee Shops

The COVID-19 pandemic has brought significant changes to various aspects of life, including the business world. Coffee shops that used to be crowded with customers have had to adjust to a new, challenging reality. This study reveals how marketing strategies implemented during the pandemic—including servicescape, price discounts, and social media marketing—impact consumer purchase intentions in the post-pandemic era. These findings provide important insights for business actors in dealing with the ever-evolving changes in consumer preferences.

Servicescape: From Aesthetics to Comfort and Security

Servicescape, or the physical environment of a coffee shop, has long been recognized as an important factor in attracting consumers. However, this study shows that in the post-pandemic era, the role of servicescape has undergone a significant transformation. While previously aesthetic elements such as interior design and decoration were the main attractions, consumers now prioritize aspects of cleanliness, safety, and comfort. A clean and well-maintained environment provides a sense of security for consumers, which is a determining factor in their purchasing decisions. This reflects a fundamental shift in values, where consumers now value a comfortable and safe experience over simply an attractive visual appearance.

Price Discounts: Shifting Consumer Focus to Product Value

Price discounts, which were one of the most effective marketing strategies during the pandemic, are now showing a decline in their influence on consumer purchase intentions. Consumers appear to be shifting their focus from short-term financial incentives to long-term product and experience value. They prefer products that offer superior quality and a satisfying experience, rather than simply looking for a cheap price. This shift suggests that consumers in the post-pandemic era are more selective and tend to value long-term quality and value over temporary price cuts.

²⁵ Albérico Travassos Rosário a, Joana Carmo Dias b 2023 How has data-driven marketing evolved: Challenges and opportunities with emerging technologies International Journal of Information Management Data Insights Volume 3, Issue

²⁶ Lars Kurznack Raymond Timmer 2019 How to create value and enhance competitiveness in the age of disruption and short-termism Transforming organizational capabilities series KPMG

Social Media Marketing: Staying Connected in a Digital World

Amid the social restrictions imposed during the pandemic, social media marketing has become an important tool in maintaining the relationship between coffee shops and their consumers. This study confirms that in the post-pandemic era, social media still plays an important role in attracting and maintaining consumer interest. Relevant and interactive content is key in building emotional connections with consumers. Coffee shops that are active on social media can continue to establish strong communication with consumers, provide the latest information, and build loyalty through meaningful interactions. This shows that social media marketing is not just about product promotion, but also about creating rich and connected digital experiences with audiences.

Implications for Business Actors: Building Adaptive Strategies

The findings of this study provide several important implications for businesses, especially in the coffee shop industry. First, there is a need to adapt the servicescape to suit new consumer preferences, with a focus on cleanliness, safety, and comfort. Second, price discount strategies may need to be re-evaluated, given the shift in consumer focus to product value and quality. Third, social media marketing must continue to be optimized as a tool to maintain consumer connectivity in the digital world.

Overall, this study highlights the importance of adaptation in marketing strategies in the post-pandemic era. Business actors need to understand changes in consumer behavior and respond to them with a holistic and integrated approach. In this way, coffee shops in Jakarta can not only survive but also thrive amidst the ever-changing business landscape. The right adaptation will be the key to success in the future, where consumers increasingly prioritize convenience, safety, and value in every purchasing decision.

Coffee Shop Marketing Strategy Transformation in Jakarta: Adaptation in the Post-Pandemic Era

The COVID-19 pandemic has shaken various aspects of life, including the dynamics of the coffee shop industry. This study reveals the relevance of changes in marketing strategies implemented in the post-pandemic era, especially in Jakarta. In this context of uncertainty, consumer preferences have shifted significantly, forcing business actors to review their approach to attracting and retaining customers. Before the pandemic, marketing strategies such as servicescape—which includes the aesthetic elements and physical layout of a coffee shop—and social media marketing played a significant role in attracting consumers. However, in the post-pandemic era, consumer priorities have changed. Price discounts, which used to be the main weapon in attracting consumers, are now starting to lose their influence. Consumers are no longer just looking for cheap prices, but rather value the quality of the experience offered by the coffee shop. Cleanliness, safety, and comfort are now the main elements that determine their purchasing decisions.

In this study, it is seen that consumers in Jakarta are increasingly demanding higher standards in terms of cleanliness and safety.²⁷ They are not only looking for a comfortable place to enjoy a cup of coffee, but also a place that provides a sense of security amidst health concerns. This suggests that the servicescape must adapt to meet changing consumer expectations. Coffee shops must emphasize maintaining cleanliness, spatial layouts that support social distancing, and environments that provide psychological comfort.

In addition, social media marketing remains an important element in maintaining relationships with consumers. However, in the post-pandemic era, this approach must go beyond product promotion.

²⁷ Jan Mei Soon a, Iwan Vanany b, Ikarastika Rahayu Abdul Wahab c, Ruhil Hayati Hamdan d, Mohd Hafiz Jamaludin c
2021 Food safety and evaluation of intention to practice safe eating out measures during COVID-19: Cross sectional study in Indonesia and Malaysia Food Control

Interactive and relevant content is key to building emotional connections with consumers. Consumers are looking for more than just transactions; they are looking for meaningful experiences and feeling connected to the brands they choose. Therefore, social media marketing must focus on how to build and maintain deeper and more personal relationships with consumers.

Price discounts, once a major drawcard, must now be re-evaluated in marketing strategies. While they can still be used as an additional incentive, the main focus must shift to how to provide long-term value to consumers. Consumers in the post-pandemic era are more selective, and they value products and services that offer quality and safety more than just low prices.²⁸ This suggests that businesses need to adapt their approach to meet new consumer needs and expectations.

So adaptation is key in facing challenges in the post-pandemic era. Coffee shops in Jakarta must understand that consumer preferences have changed and they need to respond to these changes with a more holistic strategy. Focusing on cleanliness, safety, and quality experiences must be top priorities in every aspect of business operations. By integrating these elements into their marketing strategy, coffee shops can stay relevant and successful in this ever-evolving business landscape.

Thus, this study confirms that in the post-pandemic era, marketing strategies must go beyond conventional approaches and be oriented towards meeting more complex and dynamic consumer needs. Successful coffee shops are those that are able to offer more than just products, but also experiences full of value and trust, which are the basic needs of consumers today.

Social Media Marketing in the Post-Pandemic Era: Maintaining Loyalty and Attracting New Consumers
In the post-pandemic era, social media marketing remains a highly effective tool in maintaining consumer loyalty and attracting new customers. However, this marketing strategy needs to be adjusted to remain relevant to changing consumer behavior and needs. Consumers today are more sensitive to health and safety issues, which are their top priorities when choosing a place to shop or relax, including coffee shops.

Social media marketing should be more than just a promotional tool; it should be a means to build genuine, deep communication with consumers. In the post-pandemic era, the content offered through social media should reflect the current situation and concerns of consumers. Highlighting the health protocols implemented in a coffee shop, for example, can be an effective way to provide a sense of security to consumers. Consumers want to know that the place they visit has taken the right steps to protect them. By displaying this information transparently on social media, coffee shops can build stronger trust with consumers.

Additionally, more personal and engaging digital interactions are becoming increasingly important. Consumers are seeking deeper connections with the brands they choose, and social media offers the ideal platform to create these relationships. Interactive content, such as Q&A sessions, polls, or customer stories, can make consumers feel more engaged and valued. This type of interaction not only increases customer loyalty, but also attracts new customers who may be attracted to a more personal and responsive approach.

On the other hand, price discounts, which were the main attraction during the pandemic, are now starting to lose their appeal as a determining factor in purchasing decisions. Post-pandemic consumers tend to be more selective and focus on the quality and safety of the products or services they choose.²⁹ They are no longer just looking for cheaper prices, but rather appreciate the value offered in the form of

²⁸ Gary Mortimer a , María Lucila Osorio Andrade b, Syed Muhammad Fazal-e-Hasan c 2024 From traditional to transformed: Examining the pre- and post-COVID consumers' shopping mall experiences *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*

²⁹ Liana Stanca, Dan-Cristian Dabija, Veronica Câmpian 2023 Qualitative analysis of customer behavior in the retail industry during the COVID-19 pandemic: A word-cloud and sentiment analysis approach *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*

product quality, good service, and security assurance. This reflects a shift in consumer priorities, where they are willing to pay more for a better and safer experience.

These changes require businesses, including coffee shops, to review their marketing strategies. Price discounts can still be part of the strategy, but they are no longer the main focus. Instead, efforts should be directed at improving the quality of products and services, as well as effective communication through social media to emphasize these values to consumers.

So in the post-pandemic era, social media marketing remains a vital component of business strategy, but with a more tailored focus to changing consumer needs and expectations. Highlighting health protocols, offering more personalized digital interactions, and focusing on value over price are all important steps that coffee shops should take to retain consumer loyalty and attract new customers. By adopting this more holistic and responsive approach, coffee shops in Jakarta can continue to thrive and thrive in this changing business landscape.

Adapting Coffee Shop Marketing Strategies in Jakarta: The Key to Success in the Post-Pandemic Era
The COVID-19 pandemic has changed many aspects of life, including the way consumers interact with businesses, especially in the coffee shop sector. In this context, this study emphasizes how important it is for coffee shop business players in Jakarta to continue to adjust their marketing strategies to stay relevant to changing consumer preferences in the post-pandemic era. Consumers are no longer just looking for a comfortable place to enjoy a cup of coffee, but also demand a safe, quality, and healthy experience.

In facing these challenges, adaptation is key. Coffee shop business players must be able to read these new dynamics and respond to them with a more holistic strategy that focuses on consumer needs.³⁰ This study reveals that aspects such as cleanliness, safety, and comfort are now the top priorities for consumers in choosing a coffee shop. Therefore, a servicescape strategy that emphasizes these elements is very important to prioritize. A clean and well-organized environment not only provides a sense of security for consumers, but also creates a more positive and enjoyable experience.

However, adaptation does not stop at the physical space. Social media marketing remains a highly effective tool for maintaining relationships with consumers and attracting new customers. In the post-pandemic era, social media marketing must be more than just promotion; it must be a medium for building genuine and interactive communication with consumers. Content that highlights the health protocols implemented, as well as offering more personal and engaging interactions, can help build consumer trust and loyalty. Social media allows coffee shops to stay connected with their consumers, provide updates, and respond to their needs quickly and appropriately.

Additionally, while price discounts can still be used as an additional incentive, the primary focus of marketing strategies should shift to providing more value in the form of quality and a satisfying experience. Post-pandemic consumers are likely to value products and services that offer assurance of quality and safety more than just low prices. This reflects a shift in how consumers assess the value of a product or service, and businesses must be ready to meet these expectations by offering more than just price cuts.

Overall, this study provides highly relevant insights for coffee shop businesses in Jakarta. Businesses that are able to adapt to this new dynamic and prioritize a safe and quality consumer experience, while still utilizing social media marketing effectively, will be more successful in retaining and increasing consumer purchase intentions. Adapting appropriately to these changing consumer preferences is not

³⁰ Admin 2024 The Coffee and Coffee Shop Industries: What Consumers Want in Coffee <https://www.mintel.com/>

just about surviving, but also about paving the way for greater success in the future.³¹ Coffee shops that are able to innovate and adapt quickly will be at the forefront of winning the hearts of consumers in this challenging era.

V. CONCLUSION

This study highlights the importance of adaptation in marketing strategies for coffee shop business actors in Jakarta, especially in facing changes in consumer preferences in the post-pandemic era. Consumers now place more emphasis on safe and quality experiences, with a focus on aspects of cleanliness, safety, and comfort in the physical environment of the coffee shop. Servicescape, which emphasizes these elements, is key in influencing consumer purchase intentions.

In addition, social media marketing continues to play a vital role in maintaining consumer loyalty and attracting new customers. However, this approach must be adapted to the post-pandemic situation, highlighting health protocols and offering more personal and engaging digital interactions. While price discounts are still relevant, consumers now value the value of quality products and services more than just financial incentives.

Overall, coffee shop businesses that are able to adapt to these new dynamics, and prioritize a safe and quality consumer experience, will be more successful in maintaining and increasing consumer purchasing intentions. Appropriate adaptation and innovation in marketing strategies are the keys to success amidst the ever-evolving business landscape in the post-pandemic era.

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